

The Impacts and State of Readiness on Implementation of Fourth Industrial Revolution in Rural Higher Education Institutions and Public Sector

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The extent of the changes in technology and its influence on the public sector takes place at a higher rate. Consequently, the rural Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and public sector are attempting to improve their service delivery by implementing digital technologies, using the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) to invalidate the traditional methods of delivering essential services. Worryingly, the two (02) sectors are reportedly taking long time to adopt and implement the use of 4IR, with the necessity of embracing the associated impacts and state of readiness largely ignored. Thus, the purpose of this study was to explore the impacts and state of readiness of rural HEIs and public sector to implement the 4IR for efficient and effective service delivery, inclusive of the usage of educational technologies and connectivism pedagogies in the HEI selectively. The qualitative research approach was employed, supported by the case study research design. Semi-structured Key Informant Interviews (KIIs), with the Interview Schedule Guide, were integrated for data collection, which were purposively solicited from thirty (30) participants, involving three (3) Senior Managers, two (2) Middle Managers, fifteen (15) employees of Vhembe District Municipality and 10 academics. This study employed inductive Textual Content Analysis (TCA) to analyse its data. This study found that most participants agree that the HIEs and public sector were not ready to fully implement the 4IR because they have not yet infused the digital roadmaps into their development and integrated plans.

Keywords: Academics, fourth industrial revolution, higher education institutions, local municipality service delivery

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operators, and various skilled and support personnel roles. The Department of Public Service and Administration (DPSA) also uses a system called Critical Occupation, Responsibilities and Expectation (CORES) to define specific roles within the Public Service Act [No. 103 of 1994] (Van Dijk, 2003). Apart from the military, the national government has generally been slower to adopt technology than the private sector. Some of these reasons are funding shortage, higher scrutiny at the public level, contracting processes which are complex, a shortage of capacity as far as Information and Communication Technology (ICT) capacity, and agency fragmentation (Hinkley, 2023).

The authors submit that the integration of 4IR into South African HEIs and the public sector to achieve 4IR readiness, particularly within rural settings, continues to face profound challenges rooted in the deep-seated digital divide. The core barriers are multilayered, encompassing inadequate digital infrastructure, the high cost of devices and data, and a significant digital literacy gap, with a majority of residents in such areas often lacking the necessary skills to engage with digital services. Lessons from other HEIs and public sectors, such as Operation Phakisa Initiative, reveal that without context-specific feasibility studies, consistent capacity building, robust support systems and technological rollouts can exacerbate existing inequalities rather than mitigate them. Therefore, a successful transition requires a comprehensive intervention framework that goes beyond mere hardware provision. This framework must include targeted infrastructure expansion, affordable subsidy measures and community-centric digital literacy programs tailored to address the exact needs of the rural community in order to make sure that technological integration truly enhances transparency, efficiency and equitable service delivery.

At some point, the slowness in the adoption of technology has made the delivery of services costly and cumbersome. The South African government's digital vision highlights the role of digital technologies in achieving the 2030 National Development Plan (NDP) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) respectively. Strategically, the policy pays attention to bringing technology into governance, education, and business for the creation of more equitable society, which is yet to be realised. When governments make a great use of technology, it holds great promise for both workers and the public that integrating technology can significantly address stock theft and other serious and organised crimes (Maluleke & Mokwena, 2022; Maluleke, 2018) and improve health sciences where the use of upcoming technologies tools like chatbots, Artificial Intelligence (AI), which are called the simulation of human intelligence by machines, the Internet of Things (IoT), which includes interconnected devices that collect and exchange health-related data in real time, Blockchain, which is a decentralised and tamper-proof ledger technology used to securely manage patient data, and wearable devices are explored for their potential applications in diagnostics, treatment, and patient monitoring, could be used to lessen the burden of both communicable and noncommunicable diseases, and to create a patient-centred decision-making healthcare system (Darwish, Korouri, Pasini, Cortez, & IsHak, 2021; Sinha, 2024).

Review of Literature

The Fourth Industrial Revolution: History and Readiness Within the Higher Education Institutions and Public Sector

The first industrial revolution happened around 10,000 years ago; it

concentrated much on farming and agriculture. The second started in the nineteenth (19th) century, and focused on mass production, electricity and the assembly of lines, while the third started in the 1960s, during which the computer and the digital revolution were used. It focused on the development of semiconductors, mainframe computing and personal computing. Schwab (2016) claims that the 3 previous industrial revolutions set free the humankind from animal power, made mass production possible, and brought digital capabilities to billions of people. The main difference between the first (1st), second (2nd) and third (3rd) revolutions and the 4IR is the pace of change. In this sense, the 4IR is built strongly on the preceding digital revolution. It is in infancy because it is characterised by digital technologies comprising computer hardware, software, and networks.

The main focus of the 4IR is development in areas from gene sequencing to nanotechnologies, from renewables to quantum computing, rather than on machines and systems connections. Schwab (2016) describes the 4IR as the mixture of new technologies that are combining the physical, digital, and biological worlds and impacting all disciplines, economies, and industries. According to the World Economic Forum [WEF] (2026) the development of 4IR is clearly seen since the beginning of the twenty-first (21st) century. This offers the digital revolution that occurred since the middle of the third century, based on using electronics and ICT to automate production. It is characterised by a fusion of technologies that is blurring the lines between the physical, digital, and biological spheres. It is touted as a fundamental revolution forced by the universal and mobile Internet, as well as the cheaper, smaller, stronger sensors, artificial and machine learning (Schwab, 2017). The idea of 4IR is defined as radical change based on various current technologies. Although several local municipalities have smart city strategies in place or have programmes such as the provision of free Wireless-Fidelity (Wi-Fi) in libraries and other technologies in place, all of which are germane for 4IR creativities, the Vhembe District Municipality seems to be lagging behind (Ndamase, Totobayo, & Lukman, 2025). Chauke, Mamokere, and Mabeba (2023) posit that the 4IR affected everyone and influenced the world to change. It is a predicament in a world where the wealthy are progressing, but the poor are falling behind, especially in rural areas. In a third-world country with a rural majority, like South Africa, many black people will be disadvantaged by the 4IR. The 4IR has consequences for people in rural areas. The rich make up the economy of the first world, whilst the third world is largely rural. Rural areas often lag behind in development. For example, mobile phone coverage is patchy in many rural areas, but available in suburban and semi-suburban areas. The 4IR, which is technology-based, has socio-economic effects on those who live in rural areas. Rural communities are unable to function in the 4IR world, so they are not profiting from it. One of the implications of the 4IR is job loss and an increased unemployment rate due to a deficiency of necessary and potential technical skills. It is against this background that this study is founded.

Educational Technologies and Connectivism Pedagogies in Higher Education Institutions

The Teaching and Learning (T & L) practices exist in a South African context, such as 'traditional learning methods', which refers to a pedagogical technique used in a classroom setting, where an instructor / teacher serves as facilitator and manages the information

flow. Another method of T and L is called 'blended learning', which involves combining classroom instructions and online instruction (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004). According to Chan, Pierson, Koh, Gerardin, Redbird, Grusky, and Leskovec (2021), conventional pedagogy (contact-learning) is a cultural practice of instruction where students are not reluctant to participate in their own learning and the education is lecturer-centred. Online education allows students to participate in their education, which is proven to be beneficial to them. The South African universities introduced blended learning, which combines in-person instruction with online learning, due to the implications of Coronavirus Disease-2019 [COVID-19] as the main core of T and L programmes in the post-COVID-19 era (Odeku, 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic forced fundamental and rapid change in HEI (Tarrant, 2022). Over the years, the participation of academics from South Africa has grown in the 'public and private' HEIs. However, as a result of the outbreak of COVID-19, South African HEIs are undoubtedly faced with various T & L challenges (Motseki, Maluleke, & Barkhuizen, 2021). This is in relation to technophobia, as some of the introduced technologies follow 'virtual meetings through Zoom or Microsoft Teams', accepted norms for conducting lectures, which once occurred in person (contact). This pandemic also quickened the move to the online T & L approach. Negatively, the adoption of digitisation has lagged somewhat during the implementation phase; thus, the necessary shift to a remote/multimodal T & L approach had outsized effects in this regard (Tarrant, 2022).

As a result, the adoption of the multimodal T & L approach, which focuses on the online space, includes adjusting to new forms of offerings and new environments, such as the 'virtual T & L facilitated through the institutional Learning Management System (LMS) Blackboard, supported by electronic mail (e-mails), WhatsApp and other social media platforms; as a result, the virtual T & L platforms resonate with the key technologies and practices of the 'six (6), inclusive of the following aspects:

- AI.
- Blended and hybrid course models.
- Learning analytics.
- Micro-credentialing.
- Open educational resources.
- Quality online learning (Chetty, 2022).

Some of the South African rural universities are offering online T & L, as aligned with this module to facilitate academic activities remotely through internet-based platforms, digital technologies, and hybrid networks (Chang et al., 2021). According to Singh and Thurman (2019), the 'online T & L practices' can be defined as the 'T & L process involving synchronous or asynchronous communication using a variety of devices (Mobile phones & laptops, among others) that are connected to the Internet. Considerably, the multimodal T & L is a completely new phenomenon for some lecturers and students at South African Universities (Selelo & Manamela, 2022). However, the online [Technological] pedagogies have been found to have significant advantages in terms of improved high performance and the ability to continue academic programmes following the devastating outbreak, like COVID-19 (Gonzalez, De La Rubia, Hincz, Comas-Lopez, Subirats, Fort, & Sacha, 2020). Gonzalez et al. (2020) further elucidate that student performance improved significantly compared to previous years, where online technologies

implementations were not used as an alternative method of T & L. It is also pivotal to highlight that I managed to achieve more knowledge on clearly understanding the following elements of using technology in the T & L processes:

- The changing landscape of higher education.
- Toward digital fluency in the HEIs.
- Understanding the use of technology in the African/South African context.
- The applications of on-line learning tools and technology, closely looking at historical perspectives.

Subsequently, according to the 'benefits of technology-enhanced learning' shared by Chetty (2022) the following aspects remain of utmost importance:

Increased Access: For those who have access to the Internet (more affluent families).

Quality of Learning: Driver to improve the quality of learning through self-learning.

Costs and Benefits: Low cost, more affordable, large student numbers and new business opportunities.

Social Transformative Potential: Create a new middle class.

Moreover, the technologies used for effective T & L should embrace the opportunities, as depicted in Table 1:

Table 1

Trends Driving Technology Change

Societal changes	Anticipated technological interventions
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Remote work/learning ● Widening of the digital divide ● Mental health issues ● Widespread adoption of hybrid learning models ● Increased Use of Learning Technologies ● Online Faculty development (Professional development) ● Decreasing higher education funding
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Demand for new/ different workforce skills ● Uncertainty in economic models ● Climate change
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reduction in work travel ● Sustainable development ● Increase in online globalisation
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rise of Nationalism ● Public funding for higher education

Note. Source: Chetty (2022)

The '*connectivism pedagogy*' has been lauded as the '*Learning Theory for the Digital Age*' and as such seeks to describe how university students who use personalised, online and collaborative tools learn in different ways than previous generations of students. The essence of Siemens' argument is that learning today is lifelong, largely informal, and that previous human-led pedagogical roles and processes can be off-loaded onto technology. Siemens (2004) (in Govender, 2022) also criticises the 3 dominant learning theories, namely behaviourism, cognitivism, and constructivism, suggesting that they all locate learning inside the learner. Govender's (2022) counterargument is that with networked technologies, learning can now be distributed outside the learner, within personal learning communities (including the HEIs located in rural areas), and across social networks to enhance governance and growth in the digital age,

to strengthen the state capacity and economic resilience through technological transformation.

The *alignment of the connectivism pedagogies* in the South African rural HEIs, including the rural settings informs that the tuition issues in the context of contact environment and Open Distance Learning / Open Distance e-Learning (ODL/ODEL), to improve the tuition capabilities including assessment and quality assurance, use the training interventions, such as Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) training, Blackboard Learn at University of Limpopo (UL), My-University of South Africa-UNISA-and-University of KwaZulu-Natal-UKZN-myUNISA and myUKZN Moodle usage, My-Tshwane University of Technology-myTUTOR/Brightspace and myUNISA, among others forums and others are instrumental in ensuring that we reach our students at the same breath with our colleagues in residential universities.

The Impact of Implementing the Fourth Industrial Revolution in Higher Education Institutions and the Public Sector at the Local Municipality Levels

First introduced by the WEF in 2015, the 4IR or 'Industry 4.0' has grown into a catch phrase to define imminent fluctuations in worldwide business, labour and education models that stem from the arrival of 'cyber-physical systems' (Markowitz, 2019). Its introduction has come with important socio-economic opportunities, and developmental challenges which necessitate governments to respond appropriately (Chauke et al., 2023; Manda & Dhaou, 2019; Mofokeng & Grootboom, 2023; Vuma et al., 2022). The concept '4IR' denotes technologies, such as AI, quantum computing, 3-Dimensional (3D) printing and IoT. It also refers to the way these technologies are changing people's way of living, the way they work, and interact, and symbolises a massive change in the way in which the world functions when are combined, Local Government Sector Education and Training Authority [LGSETA] (2020:4). Although technology can improve the delivery of services on its innovative platforms, it also comes with many challenges in its implementation. This is especially apparent in the public sector environment, with its complicated administration and its intricate structures (Layton-Matthews & Landsberg, 2022). 4IR technology implementation in South Africa has an impact on all local spheres across all sectors (LGSETA, 2020). In particular, 4IR technology presents prospects for better government efficiency and increased productivity in service delivery (Manda & Dhaou, 2019; Mofokeng & Grootboom, 2023; Vuma et al., 2022). According to Baatjies (2019:13), the 4IR opportunities at Local Municipalities are principally based on the following characteristics:

- Building smart, connected and resilient cities, and connecting the value chain, efficiency and mutuality of the urban system and built environment (including small towns & the rural economies).
- Motivation for local action in building clean and green, healthy and sustainable communities.
- Improving governance and staying in touch with technological innovation and connecting people to their ecosystems, institutions, and services.
- Consideration of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), infrastructure investment and innovative financing.
- generating revenue and proper management of finance in view to change economic environment.
- Ensuring that communities of purpose are developed through the

enhancement of resource efficiency and transparency through solution-based and open electronic-[e] procurements.

Thani (2020:82) posits that 'there are numerous impactful challenges at the local government level.' While some authors are for the 4IR, other African scholars raise criticisms in terms of the continent's readiness to implement this revolution. However, it was established by the literature that there are certain shortcomings experienced in Africa when it comes to its readiness for the 4IR. These shortcomings are, among others, infrastructure challenges, technology-based skills shortages, stagnant economic growth, connectivity problems and load shedding. For instance, at the moment, South Africa is experiencing an escalation in corruption in all spheres of government.' Despite the poor governance at the local government in terms of the prevalence of corruptive practices that suffocate service delivery, the world is showing daily changes and technological innovation is also influencing the way people live, work, and interact with one another. Technology brings with it a new era of industrial production where technological and human systems connects more strongly than ever before: 4IR. The 4IR signifies a massive revolution in the way in which the world functions. The WEF (2015) states that it is a 'new chapter in human development, enabled by extraordinary technological advances in proportion to those of the first, second and third industrial revolutions. These developments are combining the physical, digital, and biological worlds in ways that create both great promise and potential threat. In this change, there are opportunities to alter how countries develop, where organisations can create value and harness the power of convergence technologies to create an inclusive future (LGSETA, 2020:10). The 4IR is highly knowledge-based and requires overwhelmingly new competencies.

Method

Participants

In this study, a qualitative research approach was used and it is suitable for the nature of the study, which is exploratory and descriptive. Non-probability sampling that was used in the research is purpose sampling, where the main idea of purpose sampling is the idea of selecting the sample with a specific purpose and outcome in mind. As this study was conducted during the coronavirus era (2020/2021), the authors observed COVID-19 protocols due to the outbreak and had alternative means of conducting research, by conducting the semi-structured interviews using Telephone and electronic e-mails with the selected participants to gain insight from participants. The participants of this study were purposively selected, consisting of 3 Senior Managers, 2 Middle Managers, 15, all attached to the Vhembe District Municipality and 10 academics from a rural HEI. In total, 30 participants formed part of this study. The adopted research approach was supported by the design of the case study research and educational technology in the HEIs and public sector, while adopting connectivism pedagogies. The semi-structured KIIs, with the support of the Interview Schedule Guide, were used for data collection. The collected data were analysed using inductive TCA.

Measure

All the conducted semi-structured KIIs were documented through note-taking, as well as voice recording. The authors then went through the notes and voice recordings repeatedly to become

familiar with the data in such a way that themes could be identified. To ensure that participants were comfortable with the note-taking and video recording process, they were made aware of this during the briefing process and permission was obtained prior to interviews being conducted. To understand the data obtained from the semi-structured interviews, this study used a thematic analysis method. Thematic analysis is an approach that is used to identify, analyse, and report patterns in qualitative data (Vaismoradi, Turunen, & Bondas, 2013) allowing the authors to see and make sense of shared meaning and experiences (Clarke, Braun, & Hayfield, 2015). As a starting point, the authors listened to the recordings and went through the transcripts. This allowed them to become engrossed in the research data, getting a sense of the information provided (Sutton & Austin, 2015). The authors then quantified the themes and concepts by grouping them into thematic categories (Flick, 2018). The data were then further analysed to identify subthemes, validate the data, and filter any themes that were not relevant to this study. The data was then visually organised into tables that are theme-based (Crowe, Inder, & Porter, 2015). Inductive coding was used in which the authors identified themes from interview transcripts, which were used to connect these themes to the existing literature (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Results

Emerging Study Themes from the Empirical Interviews

From the data collected through the interviews, the three (3) study themes surfaced, namely: 1) To determine the probable impact of 4IR on the rural HEI of South Africa and the Vhembe District Municipality; 2) To evaluate the state of readiness for 4IR in the South African rural HEIs and Vhembe District Municipality, and; 3) To recommend ways in which the rural HEI of South Africa and Vhembe District Municipality can best prepare for the 4IR. The listed study themes are discussed, with specific verbatim expressions shared by the participants during the semi-structured KIIs interviews. Although these interviews were conducted in separate settings, common threads from the views of the participants were recorded. Some of the shared thoughts by the participants are linked to previous literature studies presented in this study.

The Impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on Higher Education Institutions and Public Sector

When asked what are the effects of the 4IR, within HEIs and employees of Vhembe District Municipality (public sector)? Different views from the participants emerged.

“It will affect HEIs and the public sector due to increased access to services, better community participation, and faster delivery of services, and with employees, it will be exposed to more technology and will make our work easier, and I also think it will help the employee improve their performance at work” (Participant 13).

“The majority will be left jobless, since most work can be done by machines, but it can also improve productivity and as an ICT employee, it will be a stepping stone to relevant technology. It will also improve my performance since most of the systems can be accessed anywhere, so there will not be a need to use them physically at work” (Participant 19).

“The Local Municipality will spend more money and time training employees between the ages of 50 and 65 because they face mainly

more challenges in ICT, and it takes time to learn a new system and the work that is supposed to be completed in time could be left behind. New technologies make it easier to work on the project and deliver services on time” (Participant 14).

“The implementation of 4IR by the HEIs and the Municipality of Vhembe District (public sector) can affect us by replacing the labour force through the replacement by machines and robots. It can cause labour disturbance when the municipality is trying to trench workers. It can affect me as an employee by improving the way I perform my duties. Instead of using a manual type of system, I will use technology. It will also positively influence my performance and my work rate will improve. I will be more economical and save time doing my work” (Participant 11).

“The introduction of 4IR in the HEIs and the public sector will always be a challenge based on economic constraints, such as demographics, infrastructure/ resources and lack of adequate technological equipment” (Participant 28).

“The performance of duties will be enhanced, and therefore it will be much easier to achieve the institutional goals set, and it will exceed the monthly targets set, which will benefit the organisation. Performance targets will be easily achieved and the smart way to perform tasks” (Participant 17).

Based on the participants' views on the impact/effect of the 4IR in the HEI and Vhembe District Municipality (public sector) and employees, it is evident that if the municipality implements the 4IR, employees will benefit from the skills and knowledge and improve their performance and delivery of services to the community.

The State of Readiness for the Implementations of Fourth Industrial Revolution in the Higher Education Institutions and Public Sector

The participants were then asked what the Local Municipality's readiness status is toward implementation of 4IR in the HEI and public sector. From the findings, it had emerged that most of the participants did not agree with the statement because they had indicated that the Local Municipality is not yet ready for the implementation of the 4IR due to several factors that they had indicated. The question was to establish whether the participants know if the Municipality is ready for the implementation of 4IR based on their assessment, as they are working for the municipality. The participants indicated the following regarding the readiness for implementation. Some of the participants did not agree with the fact that the municipality is ready to implement 4IR.

“Not yet, I do not think we are ready for the implementation of 4IR as there is a lot that needs to be improved in terms of our technology” (Participant 5).

“Not yet due to the lack of resources and infrastructures to be developed” (Participant 6).

“I do not think the Local Municipality is ready, as no new technological equipment is provided, and no training has been conducted regarding the new technological changes yet” (Participant 11).

“I do not think that the local municipalities have the right infrastructure for 4IR” (Participant 4).

“There are no funds available for the purchase of equipment. Financial constraints and lack of commitments from top leadership” (Participant 18).

“The 4IR can be used positively to match the delivery of content in HEI, and can also be used to provide the best operational method available in the public sector; accommodating them to the respective backgrounds, including the rural environment; however, the HEIs and public sector are not ready to fully accommodate various technologies... This provides little opportunity for high-quality technological systems; adequate facilities and lack of support and training of employees ...” (Participant 25).

During the interview, some participants also noted that they agreed with the idea that the municipality is ready for the implementation of 4IR. Some said:

“Yes, I am ready as long as the equipment is available at work and I also need training, as other equipment can be difficult to operate” (Participant 11).

The other version of readiness detected was that Participant 10 indicated that the *“Local Municipality is not fully ready for the implementation of 4IR. Partially because most of our area, especially the rural areas of South Africa, are not ready for 4IR.”*

The view of the participants on the opportunities for the employees in the municipality shows that if the 4IR is implemented within the HIE and public sector, there is a need for training for the employees on the new changes for proper implementation and the development and renovation of the infrastructure, as they seem to be old and dilapidated. The study findings showcased that the interviewed participants have different views on the readiness of the implementation of 4IR in the HEI and public sector. Some indicate that the municipality is not yet ready, as infrastructures are not compatible, and there are no funds available to address the challenge. The participants indicated that for the HEIs and public sector to be ready, they should ensure that all infrastructures are revamped, and employees should be trained to equip and properly understand the system.

Discussion

The main purpose of this study was to find the participants' views on the evaluation of the state of readiness for the implementation of 4IR in the HEI and the Vhembe District Municipality (public sector), in which they expressed their opinion on whether the HEI and the Local Municipality were ready for the implementation of 4IR. They were also asked to address their views on the effect and opportunities if 4IR is implemented in the HEIs and the Local Municipality towards employees and the municipality at large. Overall, the following study themes emerged and were linked to the studies of the cited literature.

The Impact of Fourth Industrial Revolution on the Rural Higher Education Institution of South Africa and Public Sector (Vhembe District Municipality)

Limited Opportunities for the Employees on Fourth Industrial Revolution Implementations: When asked their view on the opportunities for employees when 4IR is implemented within the HEIs and the public sector, the participants indicated that there is a need for training and workshops to adapt to the new changes. Infrastructure development and renovation are also important because they are not in good condition. They further indicated that servers are in the offices where employees are working, which is not good for the health of employees. These views were supported by

(Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart & Wright, 2012) that organisations should provide training and development programs to enhance productivity, skills, and their service delivery will improve for the benefit of the community they serve.

Managerial Implications for the Fourth Industrial Revolution Implementations: Based on the response collected from different participants, the management of HEIs and the Vhembe District Municipality (public sector) needs to participate in ensuring that employees are equipped with knowledge and skills, particularly with 4IR. The manager must ensure that the employees nominated are exposed to training and workshops in relation to new technology and ICT related fields, so that they are made aware. When collecting data, it was noted that the infrastructures are not compatible with the new changes if 4IR is implemented, and managers should make it a priority if they are prepared to change. The fact that servers are located at the office where employees work is also a challenge that managers in the municipality should have already dealt with and removed the ICT equipment and placed them separately with employees because it is against the Occupational Health and Safety Act (No. 85 of 1993) and they can be held responsible. The lack of funds was one of the issues raised and without funding, no project can progress, so managers must include such projects during their budget estimate for the next financial year.

The Divided State of Readiness for Implementations of Fourth Industrial Revolution in the Higher Education Institution and Public Sector

The participants show that the HEI and the Local Municipality are not yet ready to implement 4IR because they indicate that there is a lot to do for infrastructure development and renovations. Participants further indicated that there is a lack of resources and budget constraints, although some indicated that the municipality is partially ready for technological equipment, and then the system can pop in. It is important for the municipality and its employees to show readiness for changes so that they can adapt easily, which will enhance productivity and service delivery. The view is supported by Parasuraman (2000) that technology readiness should be applied to measure an individual's feeling of embracing new technology at work to achieve goals. Organisations should be ready themselves for these technology perceptions and once they have prepared themselves, then they can easily embrace these technologies and start acquiring the profits of 4IR (Marnewick & Marnewick, 2020).

When asked to respond about their views on the effect or impact of 4IR in HEIs and the Vhembe District Municipality and employees, the participants indicated that the implementation of 4IR will positively impact them as it will enhance their performance and service delivery. They also indicated that it will help them be technologically equipped and be able to achieve the set goals and objectives of the municipality with ease. The participants also indicated that it would affect some of the employees because they would lose their jobs as everything would be operated by machines. This notion is supported by (Olaitan, Issah, & Wayi, 2021:3) that IoT is the interconnectedness of computing devices and the ability to transfer data over a network without the assistance of human-to-computer interaction.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The objectives of this study were 03 folded, namely: 1) To determine

the probable impact of 4IR on the rural HEI of South Africa and the Vhembe District Municipality; 2) To evaluate the state readiness for 4IR in the South African rural HEIs and Vhembe District Municipality; and 3) To recommend ways in which the rural HEI of South Africa and the Vhembe District Municipality can best prepare for 4IR. In *conclusion*, this study has addressed the research objectives set above, as well as answered the main research question: “What are the impacts and state of readiness for the HEI and public sector for the implementation of 4IR?” The study findings clearly showed that the HEI and the public sector are not fully ready for the implementation of the 4IR, due to outdated and dilapidated technological infrastructures. Some of the key employees of the HEIs and public sector are not trained on the new technological changes, and the Senior and Middle Managers, as well as the employees, are not sure about when and how they will approach this innovative idea. The study findings also highlighted that the HEI and Vhembe District Municipality have been plagued by poor service delivery, limited capacity, and limited resources.

Therefore, for *recommendations*, the 4IR offers the mentioned sectors the potential to leapfrog and accelerate delivery of key services through digital-enabled solutions. For South African rural HEIs and local municipalities to be in line with new technological changes and to compete with the world today, they must prioritise the installation of 4IR technologies. The noted limitations should be spearheaded by the DPSA and DHET, with other relevant public and private departments and stakeholders. The departments in question should ensure that funds are available to address the gap. For them to respond effectively with 4IR, they should consider the support of the adoption and experimentation of new technologies to increase the technological capacity of the municipality and also to ensure implementation of human development strategies to make it more creative and resilient. 'It should implement adequate policies that will offer strategies of governing techno-digital transformations and strategies of supporting leadership and human development capacities' (Lee et al., 2018:19).

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